

Effective Communication with the Czech Customers 50+ in the Financial Market

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Abstract : The paper deals with finding and describing of the effective marketing communication forms relating to the segment 50+ in the financial market in the Czech Republic. The segment 50+ can be seen as a great marketing potential in the future but unfortunately the Czech financial institutions haven't still reacted enough to this fact and they haven't prepared appropriate marketing programs for this customers' segment. Demographic aging is a fundamental characteristic of the current European population evolution but the perspective of further population aging is more noticeable in the Czech Republic. This paper is based on data from one part of primary marketing research. Paper determinates the basic problem areas as well as definition of marketing communication in the financial market, defining the primary research problem, hypothesis and primary research methodology. Finally suitable marketing communication approach to selected sub-segment at age of 50-60 years is proposed according to marketing research findings.

Keywords : population aging in the Czech Republic, segment 50+, financial services, marketing communication, marketing research, marketing communication approach

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